

Interview with domain practitioners - Consent Under Control with ProPrivacy: Business Process Compliance Verification for GDPR-Consent Requirements

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1 Background: ProPrivacy Method Design

The ProPrivacy method was designed using the design science research approach defined by Hevner et al. [1]. Design science research provides a structured framework for creating and evaluating IT artefacts that address organizational problems. The approach defines seven key aspects that guide the research process:

- (i) **Problem relevance:** The importance of GDPR compliance, particularly consent management principles, as highlighted in the introduction of the main paper.
- (ii) **Research rigour:** ProPrivacy is grounded on established standards and frameworks, including Business Process Model and Notation 2.0 (BPMN 2.0) for business process modelling and DLV (Answer Set Programming) for formal verification.
- (iii) **Design and research process:** The method followed an iterative design process involving targeted users for requirements definition and validation.
- (iv) **Artefact:** The primary outcome is the ProPrivacy method, comprising a formal framework, its DLV implementation, and guidelines in the form of a process to guide target users.
- (v) **Design evaluation:** The method was evaluated through a case study conducted with target users (APSS).
- (vi) **Research contribution:** The contribution consists of the formal framework for defining verification rules and the process-based guidelines for practitioners.
- (vii) **Research communication:** The work is communicated through this scientific publication, targeting an academic audience with a technical style.

This design science approach ensures that ProPrivacy addresses a real-world problem (GDPR compliance) while maintaining research rigour through established theoretical foundations and empirical evaluation.

2 Interview

This document presents the interview conducted with APSS experts to evaluate the ProPrivacy approach and tool. The interview was designed to gather feedback on both the current state of privacy compliance practices at APSS and the potential applicability of ProPrivacy in a real-world healthcare organization context. Understanding the perspective of domain experts is crucial for assessing the practical value of research tools and identifying opportunities for improvement.

2.1 Interview methodology

We present here the final interview that we conducted, months after the conclusion of the project, to a group of five APSS experts, composed by information system engineers with competences in privacy and software engineering. The interview was divided into two parts, in the first one we discussed about privacy in APSS and the approach they adopted for complying with the GDPR, in the second one, after a quick demo of ProPrivacy, we discuss about the method, the tool, and its applicability in APSS. The first part of the interview was structured following these questions:

- A0-What is your role and your expertise in APSS?
- A1-Can you tell us about the importance of privacy in APSS? And what about the efforts and emphasis APSS has put into compliance?
- A2-Did APSS adopt any specific method for reaching compliance with the GDPR? Did this include the use of any tool?
- A3-Was it possible to apply these methods systematically in all the organization? Would it have been important to do so? How can this be done?
- A4-What about business processes? Is there any documentation of such processes? Did you use such documentation to verify the compliance with the GDPR?
- A5-Does APSS have special requirements that are specific to the domain and that would be useful to verify over the processes?

2.2 Part A: Current privacy practices and GDPR compliance at APSS

These questions aim to understand the context of privacy management at APSS, including the importance given to privacy compliance, the methods and tools adopted, the documentation of business processes, and domain-specific requirements. The responses provide insights into the real-world challenges faced by healthcare organizations in achieving and demonstrating GDPR compliance.

2.3 Part B: Evaluation of the ProPrivacy approach and tool

The second part of the interview was structured along the following questions:

- B1-With ProPrivacy, existing BPMN 2.0 diagrams can be reused and the load of work of the analysts is reduced to the modeling of authorizations of privacy policies. How do you see the global load of work of the analysts? Does the systematic approach proposed in ProPrivacy help the analysts in this?
- B2-Do you think that the verification of the properties that we propose in ProPrivacy (minimization, ...) would support the work of complying/demonstrating compliance with the GDPR?

- B3-How would you use the custom constraint framework proposed in ProPrivacy?
- B4-Would you adopt ProPrivacy today? Or would you wait for some improvement? Would you ask for some other specific features?

These questions aim to evaluate the ProPrivacy approach from a practical perspective, assessing the perceived workload reduction, the usefulness of the verification properties, the applicability of the custom constraint framework, and the overall readiness for adoption in a real-world healthcare organization. The feedback gathered from these questions helps validate the practical relevance of the research and identifies potential improvements for future development.

References

- [1] Alan R Hevner, Salvatore T March, Jinsoo Park, and Sudha Ram. Design science in information systems research. *Management Information Systems Quarterly*, 28(1):6, 2008.